

Propulsion biomechanics of manual wheelchair users with upper limb pain

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Abstract Overuse injuries in the upper limbs like rotator cuff injuries and carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) are very common in manual wheelchair users (MWUs). Because of the high dependence of MWUs on the upper limbs, these injuries can have significant disadvantages to their quality of life (QoL). Propulsion technique is a key component in causing overuse injuries and can therefore be important for preventing or reducing injuries. This review aims to bundle information about propulsion biomechanics in MWUs with upper limb pain or injuries to help clinicians in the development of rehabilitation for these patients. A literature search using PubMed was conducted to find relevant literature. Articles were included for this review if they included a measure for pain or a grouping system based on the presence of pain. Reviews were excluded from this study. A total of nine articles were included, seven of which studied shoulder injury and two examined wrist injury. Because intervention studies about this topic have not been conducted and are difficult to perform, a causal relationship cannot be established with certainty. Propulsion forces not contributing to forward movement were suggested to cause injuries. Contradictory results were reported for motor variability. However, increasing variability without overstraining other muscle groups is suggested to reduce upper limb pain, while minimizing risk for future injury. Further research should be conducted to develop guidelines for optimal propulsion technique for MWUs with upper limb pain.

Keywords Manual wheelchair propulsion, propulsion biomechanics, upper limb injury, overuse injury

Introduction

For manual wheelchair users (MWUs), shoulder injuries and CTS are very common injuries, with reported prevalence of up to 78% (Rice, Smith et al., 2014). Because the majority of upper limb injuries in MWUs are overuse injuries, propulsion technique and its biomechanics may play a significant role in the onset and prevention of these injuries (Alm, Saraste & Norrbrink, 2008).

Determining a causal relationship between injury and propulsion biomechanics is challenging, because this would require ethically unjustifiable intervention-based or large-scale longitudinal research designs. Therefore, the current systematic review aims to bundle what is known about the relationship between wheelchair propulsion biomechanics and upper limb injury, to explore suggested causal explanations, and make recommendations for future rehabilitation.

Methods

Search strategy

For this literature review, all of the literature was gathered using the PubMed database for medical scientific literature. For the search strategy different search terms were bundled in categories using the Boolean OR and those categories were strung together with the Boolean AND. The following terms were used in this review:

1. "Wheelchairs" [MeSH Terms] OR "Disabled Persons" [MeSH Terms] OR wheelchair* [Text Word]
2. "Arthralgia" [MeSH Terms] OR "Shoulder Pain" [MeSH Terms] OR "Pain" [MeSH Terms] OR "Syndrome" [MeSH Terms] OR "Wounds and Injuries" [MeSH Terms] OR "Pathology" [MeSH Terms] OR "Shoulder Impingement Syndrome" [MeSH Terms] OR Pain* [Text Word] OR Complaint* [Text Word] OR discomfort* [Text Word] OR Injur* [Text Word]
3. Propulsion [Text Word] OR "wheelchair propulsion" [Text Word] OR "propulsion technique" [Text Word] OR biomechanics [Text Word] OR kinetics [MeSH Terms] OR kinetic* [Text Word] OR kinematic* [Text Word]
4. 1 AND 2 AND 3

In- and exclusion criteria

Articles were included for this review if they included a measure for pain or a grouping system based on the presence of pain. The pain of the MWUs needed to be in the area of the upper limbs, including the shoulder.

Articles were excluded from this study if they were only available in a language other than English and if the full text was not freely available or available to the University of Groningen. Review articles were also excluded from this study.

Data extraction

The included articles were analyzed independently to extract subject characteristics (including sample size, mean age, mean time since injury and type of disability), the type of upper limb injury, the outcome or grouping measure for pain, the outcome measures for propulsion biomechanics and the instrument that was used to measure biomechanical outcome measures. The suggested direction of causality that was mentioned in the articles was also noted and analyzed.

Results

A total of 537 articles resulted from the search strategy, of which 347 articles were screened on title and abstract, after excluding reviews and articles that did not mention biomechanical phenomena. After this screening, 30 articles remained to be fully read for eligibility. From the 30 articles that were screened on the full text, eight articles were included in the analysis of the current study. One additional study that was found in the references of one of the articles was included in the current review.

Upper limb injury

Seven out of the nine included articles focused on shoulder pain, the other two on CTS. As a measure for shoulder pain (different combinations of) three pain measures were used in the articles; self-reported pain, the visual analogue pain scale, and the wheelchair user shoulder pain index. Both studies examining CTS used nerve conductive function of the median and ulnar nerves as a measures for wrist injury.

Direction of causality

Multiple possible causal relationships have been considered to explain the biomechanical differences between MWUs with and without pain. One study mentioned that the pain in the upper limbs is responsible for the biomechanical differences between MWUs with and without pain. Jerk in the propulsion technique was found to be lower in the group with shoulder pain. Five studies proposed that the differences in the biomechanical propulsion characteristics caused the development of pain in the upper limbs. All of these studies used propulsion forces and moments as outcome measures for propulsion biomechanics. Peak propulsion forces and forces tangential to the pushrim were suggested to cause the upper limb injuries. Three studies argued that the causality could be directed in both ways. These studies all looked at variability in the propulsion pattern, either spatial variability, variability of propulsion forces or a combination. Surprisingly, both a positive and a negative relationship between variability and shoulder pain was reported and theoretically explained in the various studies researching this outcome measure.

Conclusion and discussion

Because intervention studies about this topic have not been conducted and are difficult to perform, a causal relationship cannot be established with certainty. However, high propulsion forces that are not perpendicular to the pushrim are suggested to contribute to the cause of upper limb injuries. Additionally, MWUs that experience upper limb pain tend to change their propulsion pattern to reduce the pain that they experience. Future research should be conducted to develop a propulsion technique that reduces or eliminates pain but also minimizes risk of future injury.

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